

PRINCIPLES OF USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC TEACHING

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Abstract: This thesis reflects on the principles of using innovative pedagogical technology and information technology in music education.

Key words: Music education, information technology, pedagogical technology, practical activity, culture, cognitive activity.

Introduction:

With the change of the main paradigm of modern education aimed at teaching and educating a creative, tolerant, communicative person who has mastered the values of world and national culture, has his own active approach to life, the teacher, the teacher himself there is a transition from educational activity to student's knowledge activity. Currently, the musical education system faces the task of not only preserving the best traditions of musical pedagogy, but also generalizing and implementing the most effective modern technologies.

The term "*pedagogical technologies*" appeared in the United States about forty years ago and has been interpreted in different ways, for example, A. K. Kolechenko understands pedagogical technology as "*a set of processes for the design, formation and management of knowledge, skills and attitudes in accordance with established goals*" [1, p. 150]. At the same time, the goals should be clear and measurable, and the processes should be repeatable so that other teachers can use these technologies. Although teacher creativity is welcome, teacher subjectivity should be minimized. Pedagogical technology in a new and broader sense is "*planning the entire learning and knowledge acquisition process, taking into account human and technical resources and taking into account the interaction between them, to achieve the highest efficiency of education, as a systematic method of application and evaluation*" [2, p.205].

The main characteristics of pedagogical technologies: conceptuality, consistency, formation of didactic goals (*didactic procedures that include tools for monitoring the effectiveness of the educational process*), innovation, acceptability, reproducibility, management, efficiency. The task of the teacher includes serious preparatory work aimed at determining the goals and tasks, principles and methods of teaching, the content of lessons, designing clear

perspectives, choosing the topic of projects that expand the worldview of students, designing and creating specific processes in the lesson. In such conditions, a new type of cooperation between a teacher and a student, a unique educational dialogue of participants in pedagogical interaction, a single aesthetic space, the formation of a socio-cultural environment of education, coordination of classroom and extracurricular activities, educational and extracurricular activities come first.

In recent years, the flow of technologies has increased so much that it became necessary to classify them and analyze trends.

Technologies are classified according to the direction of teaching, education, development, diagnostics. Analyzing the technologies in the musical education system, we summarized certain technologies based on G. K. Selevko's work on modern educational technologies [3]. Classification of modern musical education is based on the following principles:

- according to the level of application: general pedagogical, specific methodological (subject) and local (modular) technologies;
- on a philosophical basis: humanistic, anthroposophical;
- according to the leading factor of mental development: sociogenic, psychogenic;
- according to the scientific concept: interiorizer, developing;
- focused on personal structures: informational, operational, emotional-artistic and emotional-ethical, self-development technologies, heuristic (development of creative abilities) and practical (formation of an effective and practical field);
- according to the nature of the content: education and upbringing, general education and vocationally oriented, as well as monotecnological (based on the dominant concept), polytechnic (including elements of various monotecnologies), penetrating (technologies whose elements are included in other technologies);
- according to the type of organization and management of cognitive activity: cyclic interaction of the teacher with the student (with control, self-control and mutual control), directed interaction (individual), automated (using educational tools);
- by teaching methods and tools: programmed teaching, problem-based teaching, educational development, self-development, dialogic, communicative, game, creative;

- according to the category of students: public (traditional) school, compensatory educational technologies (pedagogical correction, support, leveling), advanced technologies (in-depth study of music sciences, professional music education).

Despite the important list of bases on which technologies are classified, it does not reflect the diversity of modern innovations in the multi-level musical education system, which is an integrated, continuous system by age criteria and training level, general education and professional integrated into the training system. In this study, we consider the most used technologies in music education: multimedia, modular teaching technologies, ethnopedagogical technologies using folk pedagogy methods.

Multimedia technologies have an advantage over others - interactivity, which includes the opportunity for students to participate in the learning process in the form of questions and answers. "*Multimedia technology means a set of hardware and software tools that allow a person to perceive information through several senses at the same time. At the same time, information appears in the most familiar forms for a modern person: audio information (sound), video information, animation (animation, animation)*" [4, p. 160]. A distinctive feature of such technologies is multi-functionality, flexibility and versatility, individual approach, acceleration of the educational process, enrichment of the information environment.

In the development of pedagogical technologies in the musical education system, audio and video educational materials are of particular importance, and they depend on the level of technical equipment of the educational institution, not only tape recorders, VCRs, but also laser compact discs, computer educational programs dependent, they allow for a differentiated approach to each student. There is no need to prove how effective the process of mastering new musical material is with video information, animation, how much the attention of students to the content of the educational material presented by the teacher is activated, and the interest in new knowledge is increasing. The learning process becomes more emotional, involving more emotions, which increases the quality of memorizing musical material.

The difficulty of using modern multimedia technologies is that not every teacher has enough computer technology and software. We need music education professionals who can use these technologies. An important feature of the use of computer technologies is also the transfer of the student's cognitive

and psychological apparatus to a special virtual mode. The preparatory stage of practical use of computer technologies can be a didactic game.

The prospect of using multimedia technologies is seen in the further development of the following musical computer tools: music editors, encyclopedias, game programs, test and quiz programs, combined programs. The method of modeling musical reality for students is promising, it combines a variety of different forms and methods, allows for improvisational developments, creation of new sound compositions in computer interpretations.

Modern technologies used in music education include modular education, which first appeared in England and America in the 1960s. This type of education is optimal in the higher education system. Its distinctive feature is the systematization and structure of the educational material so that it includes a relatively independent part of the content of the educational discipline. In the presence of appropriate methodological guides, the functions of the teacher are under the supervision of the consultant.

Ideally, each element of the module should have its own software. Of particular importance are modular programs of various levels of complexity related to the informatization of musical education. It is important to combine the traditional forms and methods of training a musician with the new principles of informed education. As mentioned above, the transition to such an educational model is associated with technical difficulties and the training of relevant specialists.

Ethno-pedagogical technologies are among the technologies that deserve special attention. This is due to the increase in national identity, the need to introduce students to global values through their national culture. *"Ethnopedagogy is a scientific approach to the phenomenon of education and analyzes social and pedagogical processes, interactions, interactions of pedagogy with the cultural traditions of people"* [5, p. 5].

A close concept of folk pedagogy includes the use of educational traditions of a particular ethnic group, while ethnopedagogy examines the education and training systems of different peoples. The importance of folk pedagogy lies in its connection with the spiritual culture, traditions, customs, and mentality of a particular nation. Acquaintance with the spiritual culture of different peoples helps to educate a unique ethnic-cultural pluralism, to form tolerance, and to integrate with world, universal culture.

The ethno-cultural identity of the region is especially evident in the regional music culture. Spiritual values have been passed down from generation to

generation and have been a factor in the socio-cultural development of the region and its integration into the world cultural space.

Conclusion:

The analysis of modern technologies of teaching in the educational space helps to determine the priorities in the multi-level musical education system, how to organize educational activities in the field of music education to achieve the set goals, taking into account the real needs of a particular region. allowed to answer questions about At the same time, it should be noted that this thesis does not contain complete information and only allows to identify the main trends of modern musical education: a value-oriented approach to the knowledge gained in the field of musical culture; Partial information is provided on the differentiation and integration of the process of personal education, the creative synthesis of educational projects, the variability of educational programs and teaching technologies.

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